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RESEARCH PAPER

UTERINE RUPTURE: RISK FACTORS AND OUTCOMES IN A TERTIARY CENTRE IN NORTH-EASTERN NIGERIA –A FIVE-YEAR RETROSPECTIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Uterine rupture remains a catastrophic obstetric emergency in sub-Saharan Africa. This retrospective descriptive case-series at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi, analyzed 91 confirmed cases over five years (2018–2022). While the total number of deliveries during this period was unavailable to calculate a precise incidence rate, the study identified critical risk factors and outcomes. Most patients were multiparous (61.5%) and from lower socioeconomic backgrounds (87.9%). Primary risk factors included prolonged labour (56.0%), injudicious oxytocin use (56.0%), and previous uterine scars (29.7%). Surgical management involved uterine repair with bilateral tubal ligation (46.1%) or subtotal hysterectomy (42.9%). Maternal morbidity was severe, primarily due to anaemia (95.6%), with a case fatality rate of 3.3%. Fetal outcomes were dismal, with a 94.5% stillbirth rate. These findings suggest that uterine rupture in this setting is potentially preventable through improved antenatal uptake, regulated uterotonic use, and optimized referral networks. Clinical implications include the urgent need for audit-and-feedback mechanisms, such as Maternal and Perinatal Death Surveillance and Response (MPDSR), to mitigate systemic delays and improve emergency obstetric response in North-Eastern Nigeria.

Keywords: Maternal outcomes, Oxytocin misuse, Perinatal mortality, Prolonged labour, Uterine rupture.

INTRODUCTION

Uterine rupture, defined as the complete disruption of the uterine wall, is a rare event in high-income countries, where incidence remains below 7 per 10,000 deliveries due to robust intrapartum monitoring (Sayed Ahmed *et al.*, 2017; Rameez and Goonewardene, 2023). In contrast, the burden remains significantly higher in sub-Saharan Africa. Structural health-system limitations and delayed referrals contribute to incidence rates ranging from 2 to 40 per 1,000 deliveries in East and West Africa (Mukasa *et al.*, 2013; Alemu *et al.*, 2020).

In Nigeria, uterine rupture is a persistent public health concern, disproportionately affecting multiparous women (Eguzo *et al.*, 2015). Recent studies from North Central Nigeria highlight that late presentation and the misuse of oxytocics in unregulated facilities are primary drivers of hypovolemic shock and high perinatal loss (Ojurongbe *et al.*, 2023). Despite the presence of tertiary referral hubs, the "Three Delays" model, namely the delay in seeking care, reaching the facility, and receiving adequate intervention, remains a prevalent factor in maternal morbidity (Musarandega *et al.*, 2021).

Tertiary centers manage the most complex obstetric cases; therefore, analyzing their patterns of presentation and clinical outcomes is essential for refining emergency protocols. This study examines uterine rupture at a tertiary hospital in North-Eastern Nigeria to identify specific obstetric risk factors and evaluate both maternal and perinatal outcomes to guide evidence-based interventions.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Population: This five-year retrospective descriptive case-series was conducted at ATBUTH, Bauchi, covering January 2018 to December 2022. This period was selected to provide a sufficient sample size for a statistically descriptive analysis of this obstetric emergency.

Selection Criteria and Data Handling: The study included all confirmed cases of complete or incomplete uterine rupture. Exclusion criteria were limited to cases with insufficient documentation or those where the diagnosis was uncertain. To minimize reporting bias, only cases with verified operative notes or ward records were included; cases referred from outside without clinical confirmation at ATBUTH were excluded. For records with minor missing variables, data were reconstructed by cross-referencing labour, theatre, and ward registries.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were retrieved using a structured proforma by research assistants who underwent a two-day training and validation session to ensure consistency. The study utilized descriptive statistics (frequencies and proportions) via SPSS version 26.0. No inferential statistical tests were performed. Due to the retrospective nature of the study and missing institutional data on the total number of deliveries during the study period, a denominator for calculating exact incidence could not be established.

Study Variables: Information collected included maternal sociodemographic characteristics such as age, parity, educational attainment, socioeconomic status, and booking status. Clinical variables reviewed included known obstetric risk factors, presenting symptoms, type and extent of uterine rupture, and intraoperative findings. Details of surgical and supportive management, need for blood transfusion, postoperative course, duration of hospitalization, as well as maternal and perinatal outcomes were also documented. These variables were selected to provide a holistic understanding of both the determinants and consequences of uterine rupture in the study setting.

Data Management and Analysis: All retrieved data were entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows, version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). Descriptive statistics were generated to summarize frequencies, proportions, and distributions of relevant variables. Findings were presented using tables and textual descriptions to illustrate patterns, trends, and outcomes associated with uterine rupture during the study period. Data cleaning and validation were performed prior to analysis to minimize entry errors and enhance reliability.

Terminologies: To ensure clarity in the descriptive analysis, the following definitions were applied to overlapping clinical categories:

- **Prolonged Labour:** Defined as labour lasting more than 12 hours. This category includes cases of inefficient uterine activity or slow progress that may not have reached the stage of physical obstruction.

- **Prolonged Obstructed Labour:** A subset of prolonged labour where there was clinical evidence of a mechanical barrier to delivery (e.g., Bandl's ring, caput succedaneum, or molding) despite the presence of contractions.
- **Oxytocic Use:** Specifically refers to the administration of exogenous uterotonics (most commonly oxytocin or misoprostol) outside of a regulated hospital protocol or in excessive doses at peripheral facilities.
- **Fundal Pressure:** Refers to the manual application of pressure to the uppermost part of the uterus during the second stage of labour, a practice often associated with unskilled birth attendance.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of ATBUTH, Bauchi. Patient confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the research process. All extracted data were anonymized, stored securely, and used solely for the purposes of this study in accordance with institutional guidelines for retrospective research involving clinical records.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Women with Uterine Rupture (Table 1)

The study analyzed 91 women. The majority were aged 21–40 years (92.3%). High-parity women (para >4) represented 61.5% of cases. Educational and socioeconomic levels were low, with 65.9% having no formal education and 87.9% belonging to the lower socioeconomic class. Notably, only 2.2% were booked at the study institution, while 82.4% were booked at peripheral facilities, including primary health centers and private clinics.

Risk Factors Associated with Uterine Rupture (Figure 1)

The distribution of obstetric and clinical risk factors identified among the 91 women is presented in Figure 1. Prolonged labour was recorded in 51 (56.0%) cases, and an identical frequency of 51 (56.0%) was noted for oxytocic use. Prolonged obstructed labour occurred in 34 (37.4%) women.

Other factors included a previous uterine scar in 27 (29.7%) cases and fetal macrosomia in 12 (13.2%). Malpresentation or malposition was recorded in 10 (11.0%) women, while fundal pressure was noted in 9 (9.9%). Cephalopelvic disproportion (CPD) was identified in 5 (5.5%) cases, and placenta previa was present in 4 (4.4%). Retained second twin (2; 2.2%) and traditional birth attendant (TBA) manipulation (1; 1.1%) were also documented.

Management of Women with Uterine Rupture (Table 2)

Intrapartum rupture was recorded in 74 (81.3%) cases, while 17 (18.7%) were diagnosed antepartum. Clinical findings at admission included abdominal tenderness in 88 (96.7%) women, absence of fetal heart activity in 83 (91.2%), vaginal bleeding in 59 (64.8%), and easily palpable fetal parts in 57 (62.6%).

Anatomically, the anterior uterine wall was involved in 58 (63.7%) cases. Rupture occurred in the posterior wall in 19 (20.9%) cases, the lateral wall in 12 (13.2%), and the fundus in 2 (2.2%).

Surgical procedures performed included uterine repair with bilateral tubal ligation in 42 (46.1%) cases and subtotal hysterectomy in 39 (42.9%). Uterine repair without sterilization was performed in 8 (8.8%) cases, while 2 (2.2%) underwent total hysterectomy.

Regarding supportive care, 50 (54.9%) women received between one and three units of blood, and 39 (42.9%) required four or more units. Two (2.2%) women did not receive a blood transfusion.

Complications among Women with Uterine Rupture (Table 3)

Anaemia was recorded in 87 (95.6%) women, and 43 (47.3%) patients had a prolonged hospital stay. Wound sepsis occurred in 22 (24.2%) cases, and 7 (7.7%) patients were admitted to the intensive care unit. Specific organ injuries included bladder injury in 6 (6.6%) cases and rectal injury in 2 (2.2%). Additionally, renal failure developed in 3 (3.3%) patients. Maternal mortality was recorded in 3 (3.3%) cases.

Fetal Outcomes Among Women with Uterine Rupture (Figure 2)

Fetal outcome following uterine rupture was extremely poor. Out of the 91 cases reviewed, 86 (94.5%) fetuses were delivered without signs of life. Early neonatal death occurred in 4 (4.4%) newborns who were delivered alive but subsequently died within the first week of life, mostly due to severe birth asphyxia or complications related to prolonged fetal distress. Only 1 (1.1%) baby survived beyond the neonatal period.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Women with Uterine Rupture

Variables	Frequency (n =91)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
≤20	3	3.3
21–30	39	42.9
31–40	45	49.4
>40	4	4.4
Parity		
0	1	1.1
1–4	34	37.4
>4	56	61.5
Education		
None	60	65.9
Primary	20	22.0
Secondary	10	11.0
Tertiary	1	1.1
Socioeconomic status		
Upper	1	1.1
Middle	10	11.0
Lower	80	87.9
Booking status		
Booked at ATBUTH	2	2.2
Booked elsewhere	75	82.4
Unbooked	14	15.4
Total	91	100

Figure 1: Risk factors for uterine rupture among respondents

Table 2: Management Variables among Women with Uterine Rupture

Variables	Frequency (n =91)	Percentage (%)
Time of rupture		
Antepartum	17	18.7
Intrapartum	74	81.3
Clinical presentation*		
Abdominal tenderness	88	96.7
Absent fetal heart rate	83	91.2
PV bleeding	59	64.8
Easily palpable fetal parts	57	62.6
Site of rupture		
Anterior	58	63.7
Posterior	19	20.9
Lateral	12	13.2
Fundal	2	2.2
Type of surgery		
Repair + BTL	42	46.1
Subtotal hysterectomy	39	42.9
Repair only	8	8.8
Total hysterectomy	2	2.2
Units of blood transfused		
0	2	2.2
1–3	50	54.9
≥4	39	42.9

Table 3: Complications Among Women with Uterine Rupture

Variables	Frequency (n =91)	Percentage (%)
Anaemia	87	95.6
Prolonged hospital stay	43	47.3
Wound sepsis	22	24.2
ICU admission	7	7.7
Bladder injury	6	6.6
Renal failure	3	3.3
Maternal death	3	3.3
Rectal injury	2	2.2

Figure 2: Foetal outcomes among respondents

DISCUSSION

The sociodemographic profile of women in this study shows a concentration of cases among those aged 21–40 years, with a predominance of multiparity, limited formal education, and lower socioeconomic status. These findings align with descriptive patterns reported in Katsina, Nigeria (Abdulfattah Mohammed *et al.*, 2023) and in Ethiopia (Alemu *et al.*, 2020), where young reproductive-age women between the ages of 25 to 35 years, with high parity and limited education were disproportionately affected. The high frequency of cases among women with no formal education and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds suggests the presence of financial and logistical barriers that may influence the timing of presentation at a tertiary facility.

Prolonged labour, injudicious oxytocin use, and prolonged obstructed labour were the most frequently recorded risk factors. These observations are consistent with reports from Zamfara (Mohammed *et al.*, 2023) and Nasarawa (Ojurongbe *et al.*, 2023) which noted the presence of mismanaged labour and unregulated oxytocin administration in similar low-resource settings. The presence of previous uterine scar in nearly one-third of the women aligns with global patterns reported in the WHO Multicountry Survey, where poorly supervised VBAC and late referral contributed substantially to rupture. (Motomura *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, the identification of unsafe intrapartum practices, such as fundal pressure and TBA manipulation, highlights documented gaps in labour management protocols and the regulation of lower-tier facilities (Umezurike and Feyi-Waboso, 2006; Wei and Chen, 2006).

The high frequency of intrapartum rupture and the clinical presentation of abdominal tenderness and absent fetal heart tones suggest a pattern of late presentation. Surgical management, dominated by subtotal hysterectomy and repair with bilateral tubal ligation, indicates cases where extensive tissue damage was present. The requirement for blood transfusion in nearly all cases reflects the blood loss documented in previous reviews (Fofie and Baffoe, 2010). These management patterns matter because they highlight the critical importance of timely referral, rapid surgical decision-making, and adequate blood banking capacity. Maternal morbidity was characterized by a high frequency of anaemia and wound sepsis, while the maternal mortality rate of 3.3% is comparable to case fatality rates reported in Katsina (4.4%) and the Democratic Republic of Congo (8.9%). (Kitenge *et al.*, 2020; Abdulfattah Mohammed *et al.*, 2023)

Fetal outcomes were characterized by a 94.5% stillbirth rate, consistent with findings in Ethiopia and Delta State, Nigeria, where fetal mortality exceeded 85% in uterine rupture cases. (Astatikie, Limenih and Kebede, 2017; Jombo *et al.*, 2022)

CONCLUSION

Uterine rupture in this setting remains a major obstetric emergency predominantly affecting multiparous, socioeconomically disadvantaged women with limited formal education and poor antenatal care utilization. The leading risk factors were mismanaged labour, unregulated oxytocin use, obstructed labour, and previous uterine scars.

Most patients presented late with classical signs of rupture, requiring extensive surgical intervention and substantial blood transfusion. Maternal morbidity was high, and fetal outcomes were overwhelmingly poor, reflecting systemic weaknesses in intrapartum surveillance and referral pathways. These findings demonstrate that uterine rupture is largely preventable and strongly linked to avoidable delays in accessing skilled obstetric care.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To improve outcomes for uterine rupture, the following measures are recommended:

- **Audit-and-Feedback Mechanisms:** Institutionalize Maternal and Perinatal Death Surveillance and Response (MPDSR) to identify systemic gaps in every case. Additionally, conduct regular emergency obstetric drills to improve team response times for rupture and hemorrhage.
- **Health System Strengthening:** Optimize referral and transport networks to minimize delays in reaching tertiary care and ensure adequate surgical and blood banking capacity.
- **Labour Supervision:** Enforce mandatory partograph use for all deliveries and strictly regulate the distribution and administration of oxytocics in peripheral facilities.
- **Skilled Attendance:** Upgrade the skills of birth attendants in the early detection of obstructed labour and discourage harmful practices like fundal pressure and unskilled manipulations.
- **Community Education:** Expand antenatal care uptake and provide targeted counselling for women with previous uterine scars regarding safe delivery options.

LIMITATIONS

This study is subject to several limitations inherent in its design. The retrospective nature of the review means the data is dependent on the quality of existing hospital records, which may be prone to incomplete documentation. As a single-centre study in a tertiary referral hub, the findings are subject to referral bias, as the facility likely manages more severe cases than those seen at primary or secondary levels; this limits the generalizability of the results to the wider population. Furthermore, the absence of a denominator (total number of deliveries during the study period) prevents the calculation of incidence rates. Finally, the descriptive design precludes the use of inferential statistics to establish causal relationships or comparative significance.

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Ojeh Oziegbe: Statistic analysis and editing of manuscript

Nwankwo C.C: Critical review and proof reading of manuscript

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